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Financial Literacy and its Impact on Investment Decisions of Retail Investors in the Nepalese Stock Market: An Integrative Review and Pathways for Future Research

Mahesh Rana*

Abstract

Introduction: Investment has become a dynamic field and requires individuals to be active and smart in their investment decisions in today's complex financial landscape. Financial literacy furnishes individuals with the knowledge, skills, and ability to make informed decisions.

Objective: This research aims to investigate the impact of financial literacy on the investment decisions of retail investors in the Nepalese stock market and focuses on developing a conceptual framework that might be utilized for future systematic and objective inquiries in this specific area of research.

Design and Methodology: This paper has been crafted using an exploratory research approach and accomplished by using desk research. The subject matter of such exploration included related lead articles, conceptual stuff available in different textbooks, policy guidelines, related research reports, and institutional best practices in the global arena.

Results: The overall findings of the study revealed that financial literacy positively impacts investment decisions. Additionally, the study adopts decision theory, prospect theory, and theory of mental accounting to provide more insight into the impact of financial literacy on investment decisions.

Conclusions: Financial knowledge, financial behavior, financial attitude, and financial skill are the dimensions of financial literacy that influence the investment decisions of retail investors regarding risk, return, and market analytics. Further, the study concluded that financial literacy has a positive impact on investment decision-making.

Implications: The current work would be useful for the next generation of researchers in developing unique and appropriate research areas with a balance of constructs to be analyzed. It creates an archive of resources to be used in academic discourse and provides practical insights into the influence of financial literacy on investment decisions.

Paper Type: Review-based research paper.

Keywords: Financial literacy, investment decisions, decision theory, prospect theory, theory of mental accounting, modern portfolio theory, retail investors, and stock market.

Introduction

Financial literacy is defined as having the necessary knowledge and awareness, whereas investment decision-making is the act of an investor and how they interpret, predict, research, and evaluate the procedures and transactions for making a decision that includes investment risk, the concept, and procedure for making investments, etc. Financial literacy furnishes individuals with the knowledge, skills, and ability to make informed decisions (Alaaraj & Bakri, 2020; Mason & Wilson, 2000). So, financial literacy incorporates financial actions such as saving, preparing for retirement, or choosing a portfolio have historically been correlated with people's

knowledge of economics and finance (Kumari, 2020). Return analytics, risk analytics, and market analytics play an important role in investment decision-making, with the dominance of return analytics and risk analytics as they had higher weights than others (Awais et al., 2016; Balagobei & Prashanthan, 2021; Prasad et al., 2021; Singh & Sharma, 2016).

In Aggarwal et al. (2014), and Singh and Sharma (2016), scholars claimed that financial literacy is essential for making informed decisions as it involves understanding financial concepts and managing financial resources effectively. It also connects to personal finance to empower individuals to take action to improve their financial well-being and avoid financial

suffering. Thus, a clear knowledge of different fund investment techniques can help a person make smart decisions to achieve their investment goals. Financial literacy and investment competence are the main factors in successful investments (Awais et al., 2016). Therefore, the government should implement financial literacy initiatives to raise awareness of money-related issues (Janor et al., 2016). Aren and Zengin (2016) discovered that risk-averse investors prefer deposits, whereas risk-taking investors favor foreign exchange, equities, and portfolio investments. Similarly, Saputro and Lestari (2019) showed that financial literacy and risk perception have a significant effect on investment decisions, which can be used by educational institutions, policymakers, and financial service providers to design interventions and investment products.

Weerawansa and Morage (2019) sought to examine the link between behavioral finance variables and investment decision-making and revealed that local retail investors are not reaping the full benefits of the market, but foreign investors are reaping large profits through stock trading. Alaaraj and Bakri (2020) explored the link between financial literacy and investment decision-making among Southern Lebanon investors, providing insights into the relevance of financial literacy for investors to make educated investment decisions. The findings were made by Ahmed et al. (2021) on the importance of financial risk tolerance and financial literacy in stock market investment decision-making. Financial awareness is a crucial component of the investment decision-making process since it aids in investors' understanding of investments, boosts their confidence, and improves participation.

In a recent study, Prasad et al. (2021) confirmed the role of individual investors' intention to invest in the stock market for the overall national socioeconomic growth and development. For this, the scholars considered individual investors' financial literacy and investment decision as the key cause and effect. Possession of technical knowledge, broad overview, understanding of accounting information, and capacity to analyze market information were considered as the key constructs of financial literacy. The major investment decision analytics were crafted on the analysis of risk, return, and market. Hussain et al. (2022) claimed that financial literacy is important to increase financial empowerment, opportunities, and the status of the market locally and internationally and such study can help financial institutions and organizations to design and implement effective financial literacy programs and investment strategies. The study by Mirosea and Hajar (2023) is notable in the field of business research because it gives evidence of the influence of financial literacy and financial behavior on investment decisions, particularly for individual investors. This research study contributes to the current literature on financial literacy and investing behavior.

In the context of the Nepalese stock market, Thapa and Kc (2020) highlighted the low level of financial literacy among Nepalese stock market investors and identified the key constructs such as investment experience, risk tolerance, and investment goal that affect their financial decision-making. The study provides insights into the need for financial

education and empowerment of individuals to make sound financial decisions and achieve financial well-being. Thus, the study contributes to the growing body of research on financial literacy and its importance in making effective financial decisions. Similarly, Shrestha (2020) concluded that the investment decision of Nepalese investors is more influenced by company-related variables (CRV) than market-related variables (MRV) and risk and return-related variables (RRV), and the results revealed that the majority of investors prefer to buy stocks from the primary market, analyze the company before making investment decisions, monitor their portfolio occasionally, and use their savings for making investments in the stock market. Thus, the study is significant for understanding the investment behavior of Nepalese investors and providing insights into the factors that influence their investment decisions.

Financial knowledge, financial behavior, and financial attitude are constructs for measuring financial literacy that have a substantial favorable influence on stock market involvement among Nepalese investors (Lamichhane, 2022). According to the study, the government, policymakers, and regulatory authorities should implement effective policies and programs to boost individual investors' financial understanding, positive behavior, and attitude to attract more stock market participants. The link between financial literacy and stock market involvement among Nepalese students was examined by Acharya and Hamal (2022), who claimed that the study's conclusions may be utilized to create financial literacy programs for students and encourage stock market participation. Therefore, investment decisions related to stock market products are complex and require financial literacy to maximize returns. The government should take steps to improve retail investors' financial literacy to promote the financial growth and development of the country.

In the world of research, many studies used financial knowledge (accounting information, market information, broad overview, and technical knowledge), financial attitude, financial behavior, and financial skill as the constructs of financial literacy whereas the studies analyzed return, risk, and market analytics as the factors influencing investment decision. The existing body of literature confirmed that the financial literacy of Nepalese retail investors is low and financial literacy has a significant impact on effective investment decisions regarding the stock market. The current work would be useful for the next generation of researchers in developing unique and appropriate research areas with a balance of constructs to be analyzed. Further, it creates an archive of resources to be used in academic discourse and provides practical insights into the influence of financial literacy on investment decisions. Thus, the current study aims to determine the impact of financial literacy on the investment decisions of retail investors in the Nepalese stock market i.e. Nepal Stock Exchange (NEPSE), and focuses on developing a conceptual framework that might be utilized for future systematic and objective inquiries in this specific area of research.

Review of Literature

This section presents a depth review of related studies on financial literacy and investment decisions, with a specific focus on the impact of financial literacy on the investment decisions of retail investors in the stock market. A major emphasis has been placed on reviewing the underlying outcomes of financial literacy and its influences on investment decisions. The review attempts to identify gaps in the literature and provide insights into the research development of this topic. The researcher evaluates linked philosophical viewpoints, policy texts, empirical studies, and institutional best practices as the major pieces of work. It also evaluates the case studies to produce appropriate and novel structures for designing attractive routes to systematic and objective investigations in the specialized field of study.

Review of Conceptual Perspectives

Systematic reviews of decision theory, prospect theory, the theory of mental accounting, and modern portfolio theory (MPT) have been considered to create a strong conceptual and theoretical basis supporting the present idea and establishing conceptual paths of study.

Decision theory: North (1968) developed decision theory. Decision theory studies rational decision-making and evaluates choices based on outcomes. The idea is concerned with people's perceptions and behaviors. Decision theory is divided into two versions: prescriptive and descriptive. According to the prescriptive version, an individual should do the action that maximizes predicted utility. According to the description version, an individual chooses the path of action that maximizes predicted utility. In these instances, a decision support system may be extremely beneficial in reducing the risk of possible losses due to poor investment decisions (Kamau, 2011; Kariuki, 2013; Musundi, 2014).

Investment decision-making is a critical process that is influenced by the unique characteristics of individuals (Musundi, 2014). Individuals make decisions based on a variety of criteria, including judgment, free riding, risk, option overload, and ambiguity, which may be difficult for investors and financial experts to navigate. That's why, decision theory contributes to the influence of financial literacy on investment decisions in stock markets by providing a rational framework for evaluating risks, assessing alternatives, considering uncertainty and information, mitigating biases, and optimizing portfolios. By applying decision theory principles, financially literate individuals can make more informed and effective investment decisions that align with their financial goals and risk preferences.

Prospect theory: The behavioral economists Daniel Kahneman and Amos Tversky created the prospect theory in 1979. It posits that people's decisions are influenced more by the potential gains or losses of an option, rather than its objective value (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979). Thus, prospect theory suggests that individuals evaluate potential outcomes as gains. People generally feel the pain of losses more accurately than

the pleasure of gains and are risk-averse when facing potential losses. Prospect theory has been influential in shaping economic and financial decision-making research, and has also been applied to other fields such as health and law (Mc Dermott, 2001).

According to Akims and Jagongo (2017), investors react differently to identical events whether offered in terms of gains or losses. Investors are prepared to take greater risks to prevent a potential loss than to achieve a gain, and when faced with the option of a gamble that might enhance or decrease the certainty gain, they are more inclined to select the sure gain. Prospect theory may be used to explain investor emotion and irrational decision-making, as well as to assess investor investment decision behavior. Prospect theory's value function is S-type, indicating that investors prefer to sell shares early in a profit state rather than take certain risks. While they tend to hold stocks that are in the red and have unknown risks (Wan, 2018). Hence, the theory contributes to the influence of financial literacy on investment decisions in stock markets by providing insights into risk perception, loss aversion, framing effects, reference points, non-linear utility, and heuristics. Financial literacy empowers investors to understand and navigate these psychological biases, make more informed decisions, and align their investment choices with their financial goals and risk preferences.

Theory of mental accounting: The collection of cognitive processes that people and families employ to plan, assess, and keep track of their financial actions is known as mental accounting. It consists of three parts: assignment of activities to certain accounts, ex-ante and ex-post cost-benefit evaluations, and the frequency of account evaluation and "choice bracketing." These elements are crucial for comprehending how decisions are formed and later assessed, as well as how results are viewed and experienced (R. H. Thaler, 1999). Musundi (2014), Shefrin and Statman (1985), and van Rooij et al. (2011) claimed that Thaler's theory of mental accounting proposes that an individual holds an asset with a sense of framing in their mind, which determines the satisfaction they expect.

Investors maintain a separate mental account for each asset, unknowingly having a personal relationship with it. This can be difficult to sell when the offer is lower than the amount they paid (R. Thaler, 1985). The Theory of Mental Accounting explains how investors view the closing of a mental account as a loss and a source of regret. Investors strive to make gains at all times, even if it means selling an asset that will surpass the purchasing price. However, if the asset is sold too quickly, regrets may still exist for the investors. The theory has implications for understanding the influence of financial literacy on investment decisions in stock markets. Thus, financial literacy empowers investors to recognize and overcome mental accounting biases, make more informed decisions, and optimize their investment choices based on a comprehensive understanding of their financial situation and goals.

Modern portfolio theory (MPT): Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT), developed by economist Harry Markowitz, is a key framework for portfolio construction and asset allocation. Harry Markowitz was an American economist in the 1950s who developed a theory of "portfolio choice" which allowed investors to analyze risk relative to their expected return. Markowitz's theory known as the Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT) attempts to maximize portfolio expected return for a given amount of portfolio risk by carefully choosing the proportions of various assets (Rani, 2012). Further, Rani (2012) claimed that the MPT bases its predictions on the idea that investors are risk averse, thus those who choose less risky portfolios would favor ones with greater projected returns. The trade-off between such portfolios is the same for all investors, but various individuals will evaluate it differently depending on their risk aversion characteristics.

The MPT is a kind of diversification, which shows how to discover the best possible diversification strategy. A technique for choosing investments that will maximize their total returns is known as modern portfolio theory (MPT). It creates a portfolio of assets using a mathematical framework to optimize the expected return for the total amount of assumed risk. The idea contends that every interest should be assessed according to how it impacts the risk and return of the entire portfolio so that an investor may create a Portfolio of various assets that will provide higher returns without carrying larger risks. Additionally, the theory provides insights into the risk-return tradeoff, diversification, the efficient frontier, asset allocation, risk management, and performance evaluation.

Policy Reviews

This section presents the policy reviews related to the regulation and governance of financial literacy and stock market investments. I selected the Nepal Rastra Bank ([NRB], 2022), the Security Board of Nepal ([SEBON], 2010), and the Government of Nepal ([GON], 2007) for the review.

The Nepal Rastra Bank (NRB) has developed a financial literacy framework to organize the NRB, BFIs, and NBFIs' financial literacy initiatives. It intends to raise people's awareness of financial services ideas, their capacity to perceive the benefits and drawbacks of financial activities, their confidence in financial behaviors, and their ability to choose the correct financial services from the market. Additionally, the framework is projected to help develop coordination and collaboration among all stakeholders to increase people's financial capabilities. Additionally, all BFIs must submit an annual evaluation report of financial literacy programs conducted by them throughout the year according to the Financial Literacy Guidelines, 2022. The NRB is responsible for monitoring financial literacy programs at the micro level ([NRB], 2022).

Chapter 8, regulation 34 of Mutual Fund Regulations, 2010 postulates the provisions relating to areas for making investments by the fund manager of a mutual fund. It states that the fund manager may invest any or all of the proceeds from the sale of units in securities that are registered with the board, securities that are offered for public sale, securities that

are listed on the stock exchange, treasury bills, debentures, and other money market instruments issued by the federal government of Nepal or government organizations receiving full guarantee or protection from the government of Nepal. Similarly, section 36 of the regulations specifies the provision relating to limitations for investments. In this perspective, the regulations restrict the fund manager from making investments from the amount of each scheme shall be as on general shares of any single body corporate, not to be more than ten percent of paid-up capital of such body corporate, on right shares or debentures issued by any single body corporate, not to be more than twenty percent of its issuance, and on the securities issued by any single body corporate, not to be more than ten percent of total asset of the scheme, etc. Further, regulation 37 postulates that investments may be done only at that foreign capital market with whom the Board has entered into an MOU for investment by obtaining approval from the government of Nepal regarding provisions of foreign investments ([SEBON], 2010).

Chapter 4 of the Security Act, 2007 specifies provisions relating to the stock exchange. The security board may define required terms under Section 39 of the Act while considering the state of the capital market, the smooth functioning of the stock market, and investor interests into consideration. Similarly, chapter 7 of the Security Act, 2007, section 76 specifies provisions related to carrying business principles by security business persons that include the business person must obtain information from customers as to their objective to make investments and provide services accordingly. Further, a business person must provide the advice required for customers to make decisions on investment in securities, avoid conflicts of own interests with the interests of customers, and carry on the securities business having regard to the interest of customers ([GON], 2007).

Review of Related Studies

This section includes an in-depth analysis of relevant research investigating the effect of financial literacy on the investment decision of retail investors in Nepal's stock market. The overall review has been written following the linked study's guiding conceptual framework.

Financial literacy and investment choices in the United Arab Emirates have a strong correlation (Hassan Al-Tamimi & Anood Bin Kalli, 2009). The results also showed a strong correlation between sound investment choices and financial literacy. Poor literacy hurts financial decision-making, as those who are illiterate are less inclined to invest in equities due to a lack of understanding of finance and bond prices, interest rates, and risk diversification (van Rooij et al., 2011). Virlics (2013) revealed that risk is an inherent component of all investments, it is essential to consider it both objectively and subjectively while making investing decisions. Similarly, Janor et al. (2016) investigated the degree of financial literacy in Malaysia and the United Kingdom using OECD questionnaire survey data and looking at socioeconomic and demographic factors that influence the frequency of financial literacy. The study provides data to guide future research and develop policies and guidelines for politicians, administrators, and

educators to incorporate appropriate financial literacy components into their training initiatives.

Nalini et al. (2016) studied the literacy level of individuals in investment decisions and suggested sustainable measures to increase awareness levels. Five factors were identified: investment decisions personally, revision of the investment, maintaining the investment portfolio, influence on personal investment, and facing the problem in investment. Dangol and Shakya (2017) suggested that male investors in the 20–30 age range, and investors with incomes of Rs. 50,001 and more among them all had better financial literacy scores. The study demonstrates that people with high and low financial literacy exhibit a range of investment behaviors. Hsiao and Tsai (2018) discovered that characteristics such as household wealth, gender, home location, and a diversity of information sources significantly influenced derivatives. Kalsum et al. (2018) showed that financial literacy positively and significantly impacts investment decisions. Investors who report greater levels of financial literacy appear to invest more wisely (Bellofatto et al., 2018).

Gangwar and Singh (2018) claimed that financial literacy is critical for making important financial decisions such as saving, borrowing, and investing. The survey found that respondents' financial literacy was low, with substantial disparities based on socio-demographic and economic characteristics. Financial attitude and financial behavior are more strongly associated with working women's financial literacy than financial knowledge (Rai et al., 2019). Thapa and Kc (2020) investigated the financial literacy level among Nepalese stock market investors and discovered that it is poor. Jiang et al. (2020) investigated the relationship between retail mutual fund investors' financial literacy and the performance of their investments, and the result revealed that women have lower financial literacy than males and higher levels of literacy have a greater effect on investment performance.

Singh and Gupta (2021) concluded that there was a significant relationship between financial literacy and decision-making, investor's attitude and decision-making, and investor's attitude and financial literacy. To examine the degree of financial literacy, stock involvement, and financial behavior among young people in Indonesia, Soekarno and Pranoto (2020) carried out the research. The results showed that female respondents had lower levels of advanced financial literacy, indicating a connection between this and stock market activity. Suresh G. (2021) studied the relationship between behavioral biases and financial literacy in investment decisions. Heuristic bias was found to be a positive connection, while framing effect, cognitive delusions, and herd mentality had detrimental effects on the development of behavioral biases. By focusing on the mediating role of financial risk tolerance, Ahmed et al. (2021) examined the influence of financial literacy on investing decision-making behavior and showed that financial literacy has a favorable and significant impact on individual investment decisions, with risk tolerance being a mediating factor.

Making wise financial decisions requires having a solid understanding of finance. A recent study by Prasad et al. (2021) found that decisions made by investors are more influenced by risk and return analytics than by market analytics. The results suggest a significant positive relationship between financial literacy and investment decision. Further, Prasad et al. (2021) contributed to the field of research by providing insights into the importance of financial literacy in making investment decisions and highlighting the need for more awareness programs to enhance financial literacy among investors. A recent study conducted by Acharya and Hamal (2022) found a strong correlation between stock market involvement and financial literacy in Nepal. The findings suggest that student participation in the stock market and financial literacy levels are both positively correlated and gender has a considerable impact on land market involvement, but no moderating influence on financial literacy level.

Review of Case Incidents on Institutional Best Practices

This part provides a thorough analysis of relevant institutional best practices as well as relevant case studies illustrating the impact of financial literacy. I looked through the MIUR Financial Education Program: Italy, State-Mandated Financial Education: United States, and Embedding Financial Education into School Curriculums: The Case of Brazil case incidents to support this.

Financial education curricula were established in secondary schools in 2007 by the Bank of Italy and the Ministry of Education, University, and Research (MIUR). The course included money and transactions, budgeting and money management, risk, rewards, and the financial environment. It was adopted for two consecutive years (Romagnoli & Trifilidis, 2013). Moreover, scholars examined the effects of the Bank of Italy's secondary school financial education program using pre- and post-tests in voluntarily participating schools throughout Italy. The test results showed that the financial knowledge of pupils improved for the program (Romagnoli & Trifilidis, 2013). Additional follow-up studies revealed that gender disparities in financial attitudes and knowledge were evident and that investing in financial education might have long-term effects. Other foreign case studies support this (Lührmann et al., 2015). Thus, the MIUR study found that boys initially had superior attitudes and understanding about money, but that the gender gap in financial literacy was closed through financial education. To eliminate persistent gender gaps, school-based financial education programs must be adopted early and target audience-relevant themes.

Testing the efficacy of financial education in enhancing financial knowledge and enhancing financial behaviors has produced inconsistent results due to the lack of uniformity in financial education. Young adults' credit practices in Texas, Georgia, and Idaho were compared by Brown et al. (2014) to examine the impact of state-mandated financial education. Three states implemented state mandates in 2007 that required students to take a financial education course and pass an exam. Data from the Federal Reserve Bank of New York/Equifax Consumer Credit Panel showed that three years after exposure to personal finance education, students had an average 29-

point higher credit score in Georgia, a 7-point higher credit score in Idaho, and a 13-point higher credit score in Texas. State-mandated financial education programs yield positive effects, with 3.6, 1, and 3.3 percentage points reductions in Georgia, Idaho, and Texas respectively.

Evidence suggests that financial education in school curriculums can improve students' financial knowledge (Bank, 2021). For instance, the Central Bank of Brazil collaborated with the Brazilian Ministry of Education to integrate financial education into 868 public high schools, reaching 20,000 students. The curriculum included interactive classroom exercises and take-home exercises, as well as teacher training and web-based learning tools. The program improved students' financial knowledge and participation in household decisions, as well as the habits of parents. Kaiser and Menkhoff

(2020) observed that school-based financial education initiatives lead to improved test scores and behavioral changes in financial behavior, but the effect on behavior is small.

Suggested Conceptual Framework for Continued Research

Based on the above conceptual review, and other relevant insights gained through the process of an overall review of literature, the present scribe has crafted a conceptual framework that can be considered as one of the pathways to undertake future studies based on this empirical exploration. The conceptual framework in Figure (1) results from various pertinent reviews of related policies, theories, leading articles, and institutional best practices that focus on the impact of financial literacy on the investment decisions of retail investors in the stock market.

Figure 1: A suggested conceptual framework

In the wake of the research gaps highlighted in the literature reviews and the background of the study objectives, the present study has developed a conceptual framework, which is assumed capable of addressing the research objectives. The framework includes financial literacy as an independent variable, risk tolerance as an intermediate variable, and investment decision as a dependent variable. The framework is depicted in Figure 1 and it highlights the relationship between financial literacy and investment decision with the intermediating role of risk tolerance.

Conclusions

Financial literacy is an important factor in making smart investment decisions for retail investors, and successful investment decisions depend on the level of financial literacy of investors. Financial knowledge, financial behavior, financial attitude, and financial skill are the dimensions of financial literacy that influence the investment decisions of retail investors regarding risk, return, and market analytics. Additionally, the study also revealed that factors such as

accounting information, market information, broad overview, and technical knowledge influenced financial literacy. Further, from the entire literature the study concluded that financial literacy has a positive impact on investment decision-making. Thus, it can be concluded that the integrative review of the pieces of the literature confirmed that the suggested conceptual framework might be utilized for future systematic and objective inquiries in this specific area of research.

Conflict of Interest

No conflict of interest prevails in this study.

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